

13. Agroforestry and the EU Soil Strategy for 2030

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EURAF is an NGO, established in Paris on 16/11/2012, with a French Registration number of [W343014937](#) and a Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](#). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries.

Agroforestry, as a sustainable land management practice, has been shown to have an important role in improving soil quality and health based on at least four decades of data gathered from the world over. A large body of papers (summarised in [Dollinger and Jose 2018](#) [Mayer et al 2022](#)) reaffirms that agroforestry can improve the major measurable soil metrics that define soil health, and show that agroforestry has the ability to (1) enrich soil organic carbon better than monocropping systems, (2) improve soil nutrient availability and soil fertility due to the presence of trees in the system, and (3) enhance soil microbial dynamics, which would positively influence soil health. It is imperative that agroforestry, as part of a multifunctional land-use strategy, should receive increased attention in our policy discussion for the future of soil and soil health.

1 The “Soil Strategy for 2030”

On the 17th November 21 the EU Commission published a Communication titled “Soil Strategy for 2030” (Com-2021-699): aiming to “reap the benefits of healthy soils for people, food, nature and climate”. It offers a policy framework to assess the threats to soil quality and to undertake soil restoration: pointing out that soil degradation effects go beyond national borders and that a lack of dedicated EU legislation has been a “major cause for the alarming state of our soils”.

The first proposal for a framework directive for the protection of soils was made in 2006 ([Com-2006-232](#)), titled the Soil Thematic Strategy. Six years later ([Com-2012-46](#)) the Commission reported on the poor implementation of this policy and underlined that at the March 2010 Environment Council a minority of Member States¹ had blocked further progress on the proposed Soil Framework Directive. In response to a resolution adopted by MEPs in April 2020 ([link](#)), a consultation and roadmap on a “new EU soil strategy” was opened in November 2020 ([ares-2020-6391319](#)) and the new publication is the response to this consultation. It is accompanied by a Staff Working Document ([SWD-2021-323](#)). The aim is to unveil a dedicated legislative proposal on soil health (the Soil Health Law), **but not until 2023, following further consultation.**

Despite this delay EURAF welcomes the [Communication's](#) recognition that **agro-ecology and agroforestry** are at the heart of sustainable soils management. This is a quote from p.13 of the document ...

- *These practices are also part of broader agro-ecological principles which are at the heart of the farm to fork and biodiversity strategies and their targets to bring back at least 10% of agricultural area under high-diversity landscape features, to reduce nutrient losses and risk and use of chemical pesticides, to increase the proportion of agricultural land under organic farming and to increase soil organic matter. There is evidence that soil carbon levels are likely to improve if organic farming is applied to agricultural production systems. **Equally, agroforestry provides many benefits for soil health and climate adaptation.** Other sustainable practices include cover cropping, crop rotation, the incorporation of crop residues, contour farming in slopes, avoid heavy machinery, the safe and compost, preventing conversion to arable land, conversion to grassland, continuous soil cover, reduced tillage and chemical inputs.*

More detail is given in the [Staff Working Document](#) from which the following quotes are taken ...

- *Land use change and unsustainable soil management have caused, and are still causing, organic and mineral soils to lose carbon, and with it part of their fertility, their capacity to absorb and retain water and the other co-benefits. Loss of SOM is highly relevant for climate change. Restoring soils that have lost SOM can be done by applying sustainable soil management (SSM), **in particular agroecology and agroforestry principles.** (p21)*

¹ UK, Germany, France, Austria, Netherlands.

- The EU Carbon Farming Initiative “Technical Guidance Handbook – setting up and implementing result-based carbon farming mechanisms in the EU”, carried out from 2018 to 2020, explored key issues, challenges, trade-offs and design options to develop carbon farming. It reviewed existing schemes that reward climate-related benefits in five promising areas: peatland restoration and rewetting, **agroforestry**, maintaining and enhancing soil organic carbon (SOC) on mineral soils, managing SOC on grasslands, and livestock farm carbon audit. It also explored how a widespread adoption of carbon farming can be triggered in the EU.
- **Agroforestry implementation** in Montpellier resulted in a 40% productivity increase while improving soil, water quality and biodiversity ([SOLMACC Project](#)) (p34)
- NGOs and Environmental Organisations are quoted as saying ... the new Soil Strategy should highlight that the climate and biodiversity crisis concur and have the same solutions: good agricultural practices that focus on preventive and restorative measures such as organic farming, **agroforestry**, regenerative farming or agroecology, mixed crop-livestock farming, precision farming, reduced pollution. (p55)

EURAF provides the following statement to aid in further consultations and discussions on the “**dedicated legislative proposal on soil health**”, aka the “Soil Health Law” which the Commission promises to publish by 2023,

Figure 1 - the influence of trees in agroforestry systems impact soil health over a greater area than just where their roots grow. (USDA National Agroforestry Center [illustration](#)).

2. Agroforestry-soil publications at EURAF Online Conference 17-19 May 2021 ([link](#))

- O1.1_10_326 Tree cover affects the soil C balance in the Mediterranean cork-oak based silvopastoral systems
- O1.1_23_244 Variation of soil organic matter in silvopastoral systems established under *Pinus sylvestris* L. with celtic pigs in Galicia (Spain)
- O1.2_13_248 Study of residual effects of sewage sludge application in a silvopastoral system on soil bacterial communities using a high-throughput sequencing technology
- O1.3_5_99 The effects of tree species composition on soil-related biodiversity in shelterbelts
- O1.3_7_283 Tree rows change the soil biodiversity abundance and repartition within the first year of plantation at an experimental agroforestry site in Ramecourt (Northern France)
- O3.2_12_41 Integrating the dynamics of soil erosion under agroforestry systems in process based dynamic crop models: challenges and the way forward
- O3.3_7_338 Does livestock grazing affect soil properties in an oak silvopastoral system? Results from a traditional system in Western Greece
- P1.1_12_247 Organic carbon in the soil of agroforestry systems, Atlantic forest remnant and other land use systems
- P1.2_1_1 The use of biochar in agroforestral soil management strengthens the retention of water and nutrients in the semi-arid valleys of the Bolivian Andes
- P1.2_21_525 Let's get comparable – a standardised soil sampling design for agroforestry systems in Germany
- P1.2_22_526 Crop yield, soil conditions and functional agrobiodiversity in temperate arable alley cropping fields throughout the first decade after tree establishment
- P1.2_8_179 The potential of economically successful innovative food and nonfood systems in limiting soil erosion by wind across EU regions
- P3.2_16_206 On-farm production of woodchip for use as a soil improver: practical implementation
- P3.2_18_313 Comparing production systems -including agroforestry type – in organic vegetable growing on the basis of soil properties, and climate
- P3.2_24_512 Agroecological approach in soil management to sustain apple organic orchards

3. Agroforestry-soil publications at EURAF Nuoro Conference 16-20 May 2022

See [Policy Briefing #16](#) for a full list of abstracts and details of conference [here](#)

- [O 1.1 10](#) Soil carbon after prescribed burnings combined with silvopasture in Galicia (NW Spain)
- [O 1.1 11](#) Preliminary results from the use of soil covers to decrease soil moisture evaporation, decrease flammable biomass buildup, and enhance regeneration in a silvopastoral system
- [O 1.1 13](#) Impact of cattle grazing on soil and stand structure in a Mediterranean silvopastoral system in Tuscany
- [O_1.1_14](#) The use of biochar and wood chips to improve the productivity of mountain meadows in an organic system
- [O 1.1 4](#) Carbon certification in agroforestry?! Assessment and recommendations
- [O 1.1 6](#) Horizontal and vertical variations of root distribution and traits, soil physical, chemical and microbial properties associated with CNP cycles in a young alley-cropping system under Mediterranean climate
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- [O 1.1 9](#) Building a global carbon database to characterise agroforestry as a natural climate solution
- [O 1.2 22](#) Ecological relations of soil fauna under long term Agroforestry system in temperate climate: results from central Italy
- [O 1.2 25](#) Potential of agroforestry systems in preserving Europe's soil biodiversity in lowland and highland
- [O 1.3 32](#) Drivers of soil erosion in a Mediterranean agrosilvopastoral system: A comparative assessment of RUSLE model predicted value and perceived soil erosion risk in southern Tuscany (Italy)
- [O 1.3 33](#) Recent land cover changes affecting agroforestry systems in Extremadura (SW Spain): An intensity analysis at regional and farm scales
- [O 3.1 83](#) Increased tree root growth due to soil management in agroforestry systems (Switzerland)
- [P 1.1 112](#) A review of carbon sequestration and storage potential of agroforestry trees in Denmark
- [P 1.1 113](#) Interactions between trees, crops and pedosphere: experiences in irrigated bioenergy-agroforestry system in Hungary
- [P 1.1 115](#) Effect of the planting system on the carbon balance components of a black locust-based agroforestry site under Mediterranean climate
- [P 1.1 119](#) GHG gas measurements in agroforestry system with different tree species and fertilisation regimes
- [P 1.1 120](#) Investigation of the effect of plant and soil conditioners on irrigated agroforestry system (industrial poplar plantation; alfalfa)
- [P 1.1 128](#) CARAT: an online tool for quantifying carbon sequestration in agroforestry systems
- [P 1.1 129](#) Contribution of mountainous silvopastoral systems on soil organic matter in Evritania, Central Greece
- [P 1.2 142](#) Intensity and channelling of soil microbiological processes under the influence of shelterbelts in Ukraine
- [P 1.3 162](#) Incorporating ecosystem services in evaluating the sustainability of innovative organic farming systems using the Public Goods tool (Europe)